

Influence of PUD Surface Treatment on Mechanical Properties of Basalt Bulked Yarn Woven Composites

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ABSTRACT

Basalt fibres are now considered as a serious alternative to glass fibres for use in composite materials as reinforcing agents. The advantages of basalt fibres over glass fibres are their low cost, low density, chemical resistance, resistance to breakage during processing, low energy content and recyclability. In this paper, basalt bulked yarn woven fabric and thermosetting epoxy resin were used to fabricate composites. In specially, polyurethane dispersion (PUD) was employed as the surface treatment for the basalt fiber-woven fabric. As we know that an important contributing parameter to ultimate performance of any composite is the fiber–matrix interface, in previous study, it was found that PUD has an excellent effect on interfacial property of normal basalt woven composite. So in this study, polyurethane dispersion (PUD) was employed as the surface treatment for the Basalt Bulked Yarn Woven Composites and the research of interfacial properties was carried out. Composite fabricated with treated and virgin basalt bulked fabric were tested with tensile test, bending test, and impact test respectively. A scanning electron microscope (SEM) was employed to observe the fracture characteristics. Finally, comparison and analysis have been carried out in order to discuss the change of mechanical property by changing the PUD treatment's pick-up ratio and improved mechanical properties compared with virgin one.

1 INTRODUCTION

The spread of polymer composite structural materials allows the development of products in all application fields that fulfill the technical requirements in the most effective way. The increasing economical and environmental demands on the reinforcements of load-bearing polymer structural materials encourage researchers to develop new, high-strength reinforcing materials and structures. As a consequence, in the last years intensive research has begun all over the world with regard to the applicability of different organic and inorganic reinforcing fibers in polymer matrices. Hence, basalt fiber of mineral origin has gained increasing attention as a reinforcing material compared to traditional glass and carbon fibers [1]. Basalt fiber is made only from basalts, not any other materials, and has good heat insulation qualities. The material is absolutely nonflammable which has high thermo durability, temperature of

long application is up to 600 °C and temperature of short term application is up to 1000 °C. It also has high

chemical durability to water, salt solutions, alkali and acids. Basalt fiber has high soundproof characteristics and vibration durability. Since the material is made without application of glue, it is not based on inorganic glue, so the material does not evolve any toxic substances under heating or open flame. The material has low hygroscopic quality eight times below of that of fiber glasses, it has strong operation durability even in damp conditions [2]. The chemical composition components of basalt are SiO₂, Al₂O₃, CaO, MgO, K₂O, Na₂O, Fe₂O₃ and FeO [3]. Because of these components, it possesses excellent properties, basalt fibers are widely used as the functional materials for concrete structure, bridge and construction reinforcement, high temperature pipe and filter, CNG cylinders, fuel tank, cable core, automotive interior, etc.

Fiber Catalogue	Density /g.cm ⁻³	Tensile Strength /MPa	Modulus /GPa	Elongation /%	Price USD/Kg
Basalt Fiber	2.65~2.8	2500~3000	84~87	3.1~6	6.00~10.00
E-Glass Fiber	2.5~2.62	1400~2600	72.5~75.5	4.7	1.30~1.50
S2-Glass Fiber	2.46	3100~4300	83~86	5.3	26.00~45.00
Carbon Fiber	1.75~1.95	3500~4400	230~800	0.5~1.5	16.00~20.00

Table 1. Property and Price of Basalt Fiber Vs. Other Fiber

However, the production cost of these fibers is much higher than that of E-glass fiber [4-6]. Basalt fiber is known to have higher tensile strength than E-glass fiber and has larger strain-to-failure than carbon fiber [7]. Furthermore, the smooth surface and reactionlessness with polymer is greatly impacting the application of basalt fiber in the field of polymer matrix composite materials.

In this study, basalt bulked yarn woven fabric was used to fabricate composites as the reinforcing materials, the Bulked Fabric characterization is listed in Table 2. In specially, polyurethane dispersion (PUD) was employed as the surface treatment for the basalt bulked yarn woven Composites and the research of interfacial properties was carried out. Composite fabricated with treated and virgin basalt bulked fabric were tested with tensile test, bending test, and impact test respectively. A scanning electron microscope (SEM) was employed to observe the fracture characteristics. Finally, comparison and analysis have been carried out in order to discuss the effect of mechanical property between using PUD surface treatment one and virgin one.

2. MATERIALS AND METHOD

Polyurethane dispersion (PUD ZF-101) was used as surface treatment agent. Thermosetting epoxy (2008) and curing agent (2008-F) was applied as the matrix system. The reinforcement used in this study was basalt bulked yarn woven fabric. Original sizing agent on the basalt fabric was removed through acetone and one type that didn't use PUD treatment was called a 0 wt% PUD sample

Fabric Thickness /mm	Warp Density root /10cm	Weft Density root /10cm	Fabric Surface Degree g/100cm ²
1.146	70	80	6.487

Table 2. Basalt Bulked Fabric characterization

Prior to molding, the weight of acetone washed basalt bulked woven fabric was measured as M_0 followed by soaking into the different PUD solutions completely for 10 seconds. Clean tissue was used to wipe out the redundant solution on treated basalt bulked woven fabric after taking out from the bath. Subsequently, the treated basalt bulked woven fabric were put in convection oven for solvent's evaporation for 1.5 hour at 140 °C.

Finally, the weight of treated basalt bulked woven fabric M_p was measured again for reference. Evaluation equation for polyurethane particle's pick-up ratio ($P\%$) at unit basalt bulked woven fabric weight was defined as Eq.1

$$P\% = \frac{(M_p - M_0)}{M_0} \cdot 100 \quad (1)$$

Where M_p corresponded to treated-weight of basalt bulked woven fabric after drying in oven, M_0 corresponded to the weight of non-treated by PUD but washed by acetone type. At current study, different treatment ratios including 0wt%, 1.0wt%, 2.0wt%, 3.6wt% , 4.2wt% and 15.0wt% were applied.

Molding method

Untreated and treated by four ratios of PUD treatment agents on basalt bulked woven fabric reinforced epoxy plates were made by hand lay-up process. Before molding, epoxy was mixed with hardener and the mass fraction of the hardener is 24.0%. After basalt woven fabrics impregnated with epoxy, the plates were kept for 24 hours in the room temperature to cure the resin and then put in an oven at 100 °C for one hour for post curing.

In order to produce plates with the desired thickness for the bending and impact test, 3 plies of untreated and treated basalt bulked woven fabric were used.

3. EXPERIMENTAL

3.1 Fiber Surface infrared spectroscopic analysis (ISA)

In order to study the effect of PUD surface treatment on basalt fiber, Nicolet Nexus-67 Fourier total reflection transform infrared spectrometer from Termo Fisher company was used to observe the chemical functional group of treated and untreated basalt fiber surface, scanning range 400-4000cm⁻¹. As sample preparation, a small amount of dry fiber powder was uniform mixed into bromide potassium crystal and grinded into tablet. The temperature of experimental environment is 20 °C, humidity is 55%.

3.2 Tensile test

For each type, 3 pieces of specimens with the geometry of 20mm X 200mm (width X length) were tested and the mean value of the data obtained was taken as the measured result (Gauge length is 100mm). And then extensometer was attached on the center of sample in order to obtain comparative accurate strain data. Tensile test was carried out by Electronic

Universal Tester (Type WDW-20) at a constant speed of 1mm/min under room temperature (22°C). In this study, the knee point stress was used to evaluate the mechanical property of composites. The knee point is a point that the material turns from elastic stage to plastic stage during loading process.

3.3 Bending test

Composite materials three point bending test employed was carried out according to GB1449-2005 standard determination method, universal testing machine was employed, three pieces of specimens with thickness $h=2 + 0.2\text{mm}$, length $L=20h$, width of $b=15 + 0.5\text{mm}$, span $l=(16 + 1)h$, radius $r_1=5\text{mm}$, the speed was controlled at 2mm/min.

3.4 Izod Impact test

Impact strength is the sample received high speed impact, the energy consumption per unit area. It describes the materials under high velocity impact resistance to impact damage ability and the material toughness, according to standard GB1843-2008, impact test using cantilever beam impact testing machine, each sample testing for 10, specimen thickness $h=2 + 0.2\text{mm}$, length $L=60\text{mm}$, width $b=10\text{mm}$.

3.5 Scanning electron microscope (SEM)

The fracture surface of the tested samples was sputtered with gold for electron conductivity before observation. The cross sectional observations of molded sample after tensile test were carried out by using a field emission scanning electron microscope (SEM Type Quanta-200). The observations were focused on state of resin impregnation, fiber/matrix interfacial interactions, and fracture morphologies to characterize interfacial bonding properties.

4. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Fiber Surface ISA

Fig.1. ISA cure of basalt fiber

From Fig. 1, it is easily to find that compared with the untreated one, basalt fiber with 2% PUD pick up ratio increases the number of polar functional group on the surface.

4.2 Tensile Test

The tensile modulus, knee point strength, tensile strength of untreated and treated composites were summarized in Table.3. And the tensile stress-strain (S-S) curves were

gathered in Fig.2. It was indicated that the PUD surface treatment on basalt bulked fabric achieved a considerable improvement in mechanical properties of composite.

PUD pick-up ratio (%)	Modulus (GPa)	Tensile Strength (MPa)	Knee point Strength (MPa)
Untreated	9.24	128	30.41
0	7.65	120	24.59
1.0	7.54	109	28.61
2.0	10.11	148	34.34
3.6	9.67	147	38.93
15.0	8.05	135	35.55

Table 3. Mechanical property of untreated and treated BF/ Epoxy composites

Fig.2. Stress-Strain curve of BF/Epoxy composites Fig.3. Stress-Strain curve of BF/Epoxy composites

As shown in Fig.3, it was easy to find that after PUD surface modifying for basalt-cloth, Young modulus of treated types increased sharply. Compared untreated type, the modulus of 2.0wt% BF/Epoxy composites went from 9.24GPa to 10.11GPa, an increase of 9.4%. However, the modulus of 15.0wt% type dropped dramatically. It was considered that the best PUD pick-up ratio is during 1.0% to 3.6%.

Knee point played an important role in processing and using of composites. Because once over this point, plastic deformation took place and when load removed, the material would not return its original dimensions. This meant mechanical property of samples would largely alter. So the improvement of knee point indicated more excellent mechanical property, such as fatigue resistance

Fig.4. Knee point curve of BF/Epoxy composites

Fig.5. Knee point comparison curve

Obviously, from Fig.4&5, it was easy to find the PUD surface modification on basalt bulked woven fabric was shown to produce the greatest increase in knee point stress. The knee point stress of PUD pick-up ratio 3.6wt% went from 30.41MPa to 38.93MPa, rising over 28% contrast to untreated type.

Similarly, an improvement in tensile strength was observed in Fig.6. The tensile strength of 2.0wt% type went up 128MPa and rose 26% to 148MPa in contrast to untreated type. Shown in the Fig. 6

Fig.6. Tensile Strength curve of BF/Epoxy composites

4.3 Bending Test

The flexural modulus and strength of untreated and treated type were summarized in Table.4, and the bending curves were gathered in Fig.7. It showed that PUD surface treatment on basalt bulked fabric achieved significant improvement in bending property of composites.

PUD pick-up ratio (%)	Flex. Modulus (GPa)	Flex. Strength (MPa)
Untreated	11.08	238
0	10.25	248
1.0	11.27	265
2.0	10.88	263
3.6	9.75	265
4.2	9.37	237

Fig.7. Bending curve of BF/Epoxy composites Table 4. flexural modulus and strength

As shown in table 4, it is found that the flexural modulus and strength increased firstly and then decreased as the pick-up ratio increased from 0wt% type to 4.2%wt%. In particular, the flexural strength increased over 10% at the pick-up ratio rank of 1.0wt%, 2.0wt% and 3.6wt% with slight influence on the flexural modulus.

As shown in figure 7, the load of treated specimens with pick-up ratio of 1wt%, 2wt%, 3wt% dropped sharply when the deflection was over 6mm. However, the load of untreated type and 0wt% specimens decreased step by step. It is speculated that the fracture mode was changed from ductile fracture mode to brittle fracture mode after the PUD surface treatment.

4.4 Izod Impact test

Impact tests are used in studying the toughness of material. A material's toughness is a factor of its ability to absorb energy during plastic deformation. Brittle materials have low toughness as a result of the small amount of plastic deformation that they can endure which is not only affected by the properties of fibers and matrix itself, but is closely related with the factors of the interface bonding between fiber and resin. From the Fig. 8 & 9, it is shown that with the increase of PUD pick up ratio, the impact strength increases. The impact strength of PUD 3wt% BF/Epoxy composites went the maximum 130kJ/m², an increase of 21% compared with PUD 0wt% sample. It is also increased by 10% compared with the untreated sample, but when the PUD pick-up ratio increased to 4%, the impact performance began to decrease. This shows that the PUD improved the adhesion between fiber and matrix, enhances the interface strength, which can effectively improve the impact strength of the composite material, but the suitable content of PUD is needed.

Fig.8. Impact strength curve of BF/Epoxy composites Fig.9. Comparison curve of Impact strength

4.5 Morphologies of BF/Epoxy composites tensile fracture

The SEM images in Fig.10 showed the surface morphologies of untreated and 0wt%, 2.0wt%, 3.6wt%, and 15wt% PUD pick-up ratio treated basalt reinforced composites. It was easy to find after surface treatment, the resin on the fiber become more and the adhesion between fiber and resin is better as PUD pick-up ratio rising. This is the reason lead to the highest knee point strength and tensile strength with 3.6wt% PUD pick up ratio.

5. CONCLUSIONS

In this study, basalt bulked yarn woven fabric is selected for the PUD surface treatment and the effect of mechanical property was evaluated on basalt composite materials. For the basalt fiber, PUD pick up ratio increases the number of polar functional group on the surface. As a result, PUD surface treatment on basalt bulked cloth influenced its mechanical property obviously. The modulus, the tensile strength and knee point strength, which was obtained from the quasi-static tensile test, improved with increasing PUD pick-up ratio. And at 3.6wt%, the tensile strength and knee point strength were higher over 28% than untreated type and reached the maximum.

Fig. 10 SEM observation of fractured composites

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